

ORGANIZATION OF THE PRODUCTION AND USE OF THE SECONDARY AGGREGATE FROM CONCRETE SLAG IN THE WORLD-WIDE OPERATION

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Abstract Attention to the issue of reuse of concrete in construction production attracted specialists in the 90s of the last century, because by this time the shortage of natural fillers began to be felt, the need for environmental protection increased, and the number of old, morally and physically obsolete buildings and structures that needed to be demolished increased significantly. In some countries, including Japan, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands and Luxembourg, there are no places left to collect, store or bury concrete waste. At the same time, in some countries, it became necessary to use limestone imported from abroad.

Keys themselves; Concrete scrap, demolition, secondary aggregate, crushed stone, disposal, construction waste, primary aggregate, reinforced concrete construction, revetment

Due to the increasing volume of demolition of one- and two-story buildings, replacement of bridge structures and road pavements, the problems of processing perishable structures and construction elements in order to obtain secondary non-ferrous construction materials are becoming more and more urgent.

In worldwide practice, the production and use of secondary filler from concrete slag is carried out according to the following three options:

1. Concrete scrap is transported by transport from the dismantling site to the secondary aggregates production plant, and the received aggregate is sent to the concrete production plant (two transport operations).

Equipment for extracting filler from concrete scrap is installed directly at the dismantling site, and the received filler is sent to the concrete production plant or the construction site (transportation operation in one transport).

3. Extraction of filler from concrete scrap and production of building structures or products based on it is organized directly at the place of dismantling (transportation in the internal transport of the plant).

In CIS countries , that 's it including In Uzbekistan , the organization of production of secondary filler obtained from concrete slag is mainly carried out according to the second option (Fig. 1.1, cycle A). The resulting secondary fill is used as a gravel bed for the foundations of the roads.

Figure 1.1. Disposal of concrete waste schemes

Concrete lomini again work with engaged in foreign of firms advanced from experience the following work release schemes seeing exit to the goal according to in Japan concrete lomini The most common scheme for recycling and reusing secondary fillers corresponds to option 3, discussed above . In order to increase the

efficiency of using concrete laminiun as a secondary filler in the composition of concrete, it is advisable to prepare such a filler at the production site with the help of a small crusher and a grinder. On the spot, it is used in the preparation of a concrete mixture and placed in the structure during the construction of a new structure. "Closed system" secondary filler production technology is widely used in the Netherlands .

Construction waste disposal We will analyze the following available schemes:

A) the building is demolished, and the resulting solid construction waste is taken to special landfills for burial;

B) the building is demolished, part of the resulting solid construction waste is taken to special landfills for burial, and the other part is taken to stationary centers for processing;

V) the building is separated into parts and concrete and reinforced concrete structures are taken to stationary centers for processing;

G) the building is disassembled and all concrete and reinforced concrete structures without a heater layer are taken to stationary centers for recycling. For burying constructions and other waste with a heater layer intended special to landfills take go thrown away

Secondary fillers are considered inferior in terms of quality compared to primary fillers, primarily due to the shape of their boron particles. In addition, they have lower density, mass per unit volume and percentage of volume in a dense body, water absorption, mass loss when testing resistance to weathering, and melting loss are higher. All these changes are related to the presence of admixture in crushed stone from cement concrete waste.

S. Nisibiyasi and others according to the data , the amount of the mixture stuck in the secondary large aggregate is 36-39%, and this amount decreases with the increase of the S/Ts ratio of the initial concrete composition. Smaller fractions of secondary aggregates contain more concrete admixture. In particles with a size of up

to 0.3 mm, the amount of the mixture reaches about 50%, while this in the secondary filler indicator quantity and from 20-25% does not exceed

Transferred analysis the following led to the conclusions :

- option b) is considered the most cost-effective disposal of construction waste from an economic point of view;
- construction waste ecological in terms of safe disposal option c) option is counted .

first time, it is biodegradable from constructions In 1946 , VNIIG (Russia) institute to obtain the finished material employee an engineer Glujge P.I. by Dneprostroy for offer did From the war next in years fillers get for war in time broken building and structures from the elements use very important was In 1947-48 exactly so studies Ploger R.R. and Graf O. (Germany) held . However later on natural noru construction materials release and construction objects delivery to give to the road being placed due to concrete and reinforced concrete from the rope recipient secondary of fillers use his own relevance much lost

European researchers wrapped up from products use opportunities back in the 1960s to study they stayed This especially mineral raw material reserves limited was , housing fund is being updated and fruit happening waste burial for empty lands shortage has been countries wide to the road was put

the CIS countries above given problems back in the 1980s to study they came This to time come don't collect reinforced concrete in factories brack issued products , concrete and reinforced concrete items of waste very big sizes get together the rest For example , of the city of Moscow in itself 16 conditioners didn't happen materials again to work intended lines to work dropped was , however natural of stone recipient a little cheaper has been bite of the stone application economic in terms of more efficient that it was for their of the majority work to be stopped take came

1980-90 in the CIS countries spiritual and physical in terms of out of date housing fund update process started First in line big non - reconstructed K -7-3, P-14, P-32, I-510 and another in the series five layered houses violation must it happened

However, the breakdown and parts to separate intended this buildings of size size their disposal _ according to fast measures to be seen just like that did Target 10-12 mln . t construction crowbar and waste disposal and 4-5 mln. t is secondary fillers work release in the eye caught was

Nationwide or , city At scale , city-wide benefits include using local raw materials with limited transportation routes, eliminating or reducing landfill sites for construction debris, repurposing some crushed stone at the recycling site for landscaping and paving, and natural resources that often have high delivery costs relative to their cost. secondary instead of fillers fillers to use is based on

As a result of the analysis of the accumulated experience in our republic and foreign countries, it is possible to draw the following conclusion, that mainly secondary crushed stone obtained from the processing of concrete scrap is used in the construction of the paving layer of access roads and low-traffic roads, in the construction of foundations under warehouses, production rooms and small mechanisms, various bases It is recommended to use it when building.

Summary

Summary in place construction practice that's it showing given that it is necessary to quality have has been bite the stone get for building and technical, technological constructions and ecological status modern including styles _ indestructible methods using initial directly from inspection transfer just like that does _ Only building and structures elements into pieces separate and them sorting , pieces primary preparation , later sorting , sorting and storage through work release all stages quality control to do posts and belongs to normative documents is available just in case modern construction requirements according to coming bite stone taken can

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